

Open-Source Software and Open-Source Hardware under the new European Product Liability Directive

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Abstract

As part of the European Green Deal, the EU aims to become fully climate-neutral, promoting sustainable innovation through a circular economy. Open-Source Software and Open-Source Hardware play a key role in this transition, enabling repairable, durable, and collaboratively designed products. However, despite their potential to contribute significantly to EU sustainability goals, many open-source developers remain hesitant to publish or commercialize their work due to legal uncertainties and liability risks. These “chilling effects” stem primarily from concerns over strict liability for defects under the existing EU Product Liability Directive (Directive 85/374/EEC). In response, the EU has adopted a revised Product Liability Directive (Directive (EU) 2024/2853) to modernize liability rules for the digital age. Notably, it explicitly excludes free and open-source software developed outside commercial contexts from strict liability and clarifies rules for digital manufacturing files and software. This article examines whether the PLD New provides the legal certainty necessary to reduce liability fears and unlock the full sustainability potential of Open-Source Software and Hardware. It introduces the concepts, stakeholders, and previous legal challenges, before analysing the directive’s impact and critically assessing whether it represents a turning point or a new obstacle for the open-source movement in Europe.

Keywords

Open Source, Product Liability, Directive (EU) 2024/2853, EU Law, Sustainability, Circular Economy

1 Introduction

As part of “The European Green Deal” the EU is striving to be the first “climate-neutral continent [sic!]” (quoted from: European Commission). This includes developing and fostering a more sustainable and circular economy (European Commission, 2020). Open-Source Software (OSS) and Open-Source Hardware (OSH) constitute an important step towards this goal (see regarding OSH: Haller, 2024, p. 9). For instance, open-source designed products are often easier to repair and refurbish which increases product lifespan and reduces e-waste (see regarding OSH: Hofer et al., 2024, pp. 231 et seq.). The open-source approach further allows society to benefit from the collective knowledge of a multitude of stakeholders, enabling more effective and sustainable product designs (see regarding OSH: Hofer et al., pp. 231 et seq.; see regarding OSS: Colonna, 2024, p. 5; Wilson/Tchantchaleishvili, 2013).

Despite its role in achieving the EU sustainability goals, there are many legal uncertainties in the open-source community, leading to caution about publishing their work (“chilling effects” are mentioned in: Kuschel/Haller, 2024, p. 150). Most importantly, many open-source designers and developers fear liability

for potential product defects (see: Haller, 2024, p. 2). Fundamentally interested parties therefore do not enter the open-source sector.

Recently, however, the EU lawmaker enacted a new Product Liability Directive (Directive (EU) 2024/2853 – in the following: “PLD New”) aiming to bring EU product liability law into the digital age (see: European Commission, Proposal, 2022). As a complete novum the directive now explicitly excludes “free and open-source software developed or supplied outside the course of a commercial activity” from strict product liability (Art. 2(2) PLD New) and provides more clarity regarding product liability for software as well as digital manufacturing files (Art. 4(1) PLD New; see 5.1.1).

This raises the question whether the PLD New will finally provide the legal clarity and liability exemptions that are necessary to reduce “chilling effects” in the open-source community and to allow the OSS and OSH movement to realize its full potential for (green) innovation.

This article will provide an overview over the PLD New and its changes to product liability by (2) briefly introducing the concepts of OSS and OSH, (3) outlining the typical stakeholders within the OSS and OSH value chain, and (4) explaining why the current EU product liability framework under Directive 85/374/EEC (in the following: “PLD Old”) gave rise to significant liability concerns within the open-source community. After establishing the key issues under the current legislative framework, the essay will (5) analyse the liability for OSS and OSH under the PLD New. Finally, it critically assesses (6) whether the legislative change will allow the OSS and OSH movement to better realize its transformative and innovative sustainability potential or, on the contrary, lead to a liability so strict that it practically means “the end of open source” as Colonna provocatively asked (Colonna, 2024, p. 1).

2 Foundations: OSS and OSH

To fully comprehend the implications of OSS and OSH for product liability, a basic understanding of the underlying concepts is crucial (regarding OSS: Colonna, 2024). Simplified, OSS describes software with a freely distributed source code and that is “royalty-free” under intellectual property law enabling developers to create and distribute modifications and derivative works (Colonna, 2024; see for the full set of requirements: Open Source Initiative, 2024). OSH tries to transfer these open-source principles to the world of physical objects (Bonvoisin, et al., 2017, p. 1). Therefore, OSH requires that using, making, commercially reusing, and accessing the hardware is “royalty-free” from an intellectual property law perspective and that its underlying documentation is made available (see: Bonvoisin, et al., 2017, pp. 3–4; see in detail: OSHWA, Statement of Principles 1.0). This particularly means that the underlying design rationales, such as 3D models, are published (see: Bonvoisin, et al., 2017, pp. 6–7). At its idealistic core, the open-source concept aims at leveraging collaborative intelligence to increase innovation for the benefit of the industry and society as a whole (Colonna, 2024, p. 17; Ackermann, 2009, p. 183). The idea is that better and more reliable products can be developed when programmers and designers share the source code or hardware design enabling anyone to contribute fixes, optimizations and enhancements (see regarding OSS: Colonna, 2024, p. 5 and Wilson/Tchantchaleishvili, 2013; see regarding OSH: Pearce, 2025). Especially OSH empowers individuals, startups, and communities to innovate in ways that were previously limited to large corporations.

3 Stakeholders and Liability Risks along the OSS and OSH Value Chains

Because of their unique aim at leveraging collaborative intelligence, the OSS and OSH value chains differ significantly from those of “closed” proprietary software and hardware. In traditional manufacturing, a single company normally oversees the design, production, and distribution of a product, centralizing responsibility and liability. In contrast, open-source projects mostly involve a decentralized network of

contributors that often work independently (see regarding OSH: Kuschel/Haller, 2024, pp. 150–151; see regarding OSS: Kennedy, 2001, p. 347, describing the development process as community-based).

In the OSH context, a designer creates the hardware blueprints (OSH designs) and makes them freely available, typically on an internet platform, where it can be downloaded by manufacturers (Kuschel/Haller, 2024, pp. 150–151). Once produced, the physical OSH is either used by the manufacturer themselves, e.g. to provide services as part of open workshops, such as Fab Labs, or sold to third-parties. Note that effectively everyone with the necessary tools – normally a 3D printer – can now become a manufacturer (Kuschel/Haller, 2024, pp. 150–151; see also: Grosskopf, 2012, p. 618, in relation to 3D printing).

Similarly, the OSS development process typically involves the collective contributions of many volunteering programmers who are usually managed by a person or group of people responsible for the OSS (Kennedy, 2001, p. 347). Their work progress is usually published on an open repository where others can access and download the source code to make their own modifications and improvements (see: Colonna, 2024, pp. 3–4).

These particularities of the OSS and OSH environment reflect in the liability landscape. The fragmentations of production steps and responsible stakeholders complicate the assignment of liability when damage emerges. Within the OSH value chain, liability risks can emerge at two key stages: (1) A defective OSH design might result in a defective physical OSH which, in turn, could cause damage to individuals or property; (2) errors during production (e.g. faulty raw materials) can lead to defects in the physical OSH that may cause damage to third parties – even when the underlying OSH design had no defect (for a more detailed overview see: Kuschel/Haller, 2024, pp. 151–152). Further problems arise when the physical OSH is later integrated into another product. Therefore, a crucial liability concern regarding OSH stems from uncertainty about the distribution of liability along the value chain. Similar difficulties also subsist in the OSS environment. Here, the main problem, besides integrated products, is assessing if and to what extent singular programmers are liable for defects in their source code contributions.

Another key liability risk follows from the fact that anyone, including non-professionals, can contribute to the OSS and OSH value chain. This raises questions regarding the applicable liability standards and how the stakeholders' diverging professionalism degrees should be considered (see 5.3).

Specifically for OSS, the applicability of product liability law is problematic as it may lead to an undermining of traditional liability exclusions found in OSS licenses (Colonna, 2024, p. 11). This causes increasing uncertainty in the open-source community as established contractual clauses cannot provide the same legal protection as before (see 5.4). In practice, product liability is therefore one of the most important areas of law regarding open-source projects.

4 European Product Liability Law in Transition: Implications for OSS and OSH

Yet, there are “great uncertainties concerning [...] product liability” within the open-source community (see regarding OSH: Haller, 2024, p. 2).

4.1 The Old European Product Liability Directive (1985)

This is by no means surprising: The current product liability law in the EU Member States is based upon the PLD Old – a legal act from 1985. It obliged Member States to implement a very strict liability regime for producers who put a defective product into circulation and thus led to an approximation of product liability laws in the EU (see: Förster, 2025, mn. 2; Katzenmeier, 2021, mn. 1). In principle, the PLD Old ensured that the manufacturer had to compensate every person who could prove that they suffered any personal or private property injury due to the defective product (see: Alheit, 2001; and roughly: Katzenmeier, 2021, mn. 1). Personal fault or negligence on part of the manufacturer was not required to bring a claim (so-called strict liability, see: Alheit, 2001, p. 195; regarding the German implementation of the PLD Old: Haller, 2024, p. 3). As the producer could not contractually exclude or limit this product

liability (Art. 12 PLD Old), they could only defend themselves by proving that one of the very few liability exceptions set out in the directive were met (Art. 7 PLD Old). In particular, they could circumvent liability by proving that the product probably was not defective when put into circulation (later-defect defense, Art. 7(b) PLD Old), was state-of-the-art when put into circulation so that the existence of the defect could not have been discovered back then (state-of-the-art defense or development-risk defense, Art. 7(e) PLD Old), or if they proved that the product was not manufactured for sale or distributed in the course of their business activity (non-commercial defense, Art. 7(c) PLD Old) (Alheit, 2001). As shown, this liability standard was extremely strict and did not address recent technological developments, like the digital and circular economy and the open-source movement (similar: Kuschel/Haller, 2024, p. 158).

4.1.1 Classifying OSS und OSH as “Products”

In particular, it was unclear whether and under what circumstances the output of open-source projects was covered by the PLD Old as it defined products as only “movables” as well as “electricity” (Art. 2 PLD Old). Certainly, this definition was met when physical items were produced based on OSH designs. However, the PLD Old provided no certainty regarding the underlying OSH design file or an OSS as they could hardly be classified as movables or electricity. Yet, just like tangible products, they had the potential to cause harm to individuals or third-party property. This led to a wide array of conflicting views in legal literature without the issues ever being resolved by the Court of Justice of the European Union (in the following: CJEU) (see regarding software: Borges, 2025; Adelberg, 2023, pp. 59–60; Fairgrieve/Rajneri, 2019; Hofmeister, 2022, pp. 359–360; regarding design files: Haller, 2024, p. 5; Leupold, et al., 2021, mn. 45; Wagner, MüKoBGB, 2024, ProdHaftG § 2 mn. 27 et seq.; Oechsler, 2018, p. 1569).

4.1.2 The Non-Commercial Defense

In practice, many open-source stakeholders simply assumed that product liability law was applicable and tried to “save” themselves by referring to the non-commercial defense. The defense provided a liability exemption if the product was not manufactured by the producer for sale or any other form of distribution for economic purposes nor manufactured or distributed by them in the course of their business (Art. 7(c) PLD Old). However, even this exemption fell short from providing legal certainty as its applicability was dependent on an overall assessment of the product’s whole distribution process (see: Spindler, 2024, mn. 83). This caused a complex casuistic:

- **Hobby projects:** OSS and OSH that were developed as hobby projects by private individuals and distributed through a private website free of charge generally fell under the non-commercial defense (see regarding OSS: Spindler, 2024, mn. 83).
- **Advertising purposes:** However, the non-commercial defense was inapplicable if the product was supplied in the context of a sponsoring campaign (Seibl, 2025, mn. 102; see for problematic constellations concerning individual contributions to OSS for professional self-representation purposes: Jaeger/Metzger, 2020, mn. 306; Spindler, 2024, mn. 83).
- **OSS and OSH developed in company structures:** Some also argued that the non-commercial defense was always inapplicable as soon as the product was developed in a company structure (Schiffner, 2002, p. 258). This view effectively limited the non-commercial defense to NPOs, research organizations, and private individuals.
- **OSS and OSH financed with public funds:** Even those institutions could not rely on the non-commercial defense as soon as the product was manufactured and used for a service financed by public funds (see: CJEU, C-203/99 – Henning Veddfald) as the source of consideration was irrelevant for establishing a commercial purpose (see: Kapoor, 2023, mn. 97). For manufacturers it did not make a difference whether they receive monetary enumeration directly from their customers or from public funds. If a manufacturer received public funds, e.g. to manufacture or use OSS or OSH to provide a specific health service as part of public health insurance, they fell under the PLD Old. Some scholars went so far as to suggest that third-party financed development

alone should automatically render the supply of that product commercial (see regarding OSS: Haller, 2024, p. 9).

- **Paid Support Services:** Further problems arose when a manufacturer distributed open-source products for free but later offered additional paid support services. Generally, this was still considered non-commercial as the economic purpose must have already been pursued during the product development phase to trigger the applicability of the PLD Old (see regarding OSS: Spindler, 2024, mn. 82; Jaeger/Metzger, 2020, mn. 305 et seq.; Schiffner, 2002, p. 258). However, the non-commercial defense was deemed inapplicable if the manufacturer deliberately intended to offer their open-source product free of charge just as a mean to later generate profit from necessary support services (Spindler, 2024, mn. 83).

Against the backdrop of this complex legal casuistic, it is clear why the application of the 40 years old product liability standards towards the emerging open-source movement has led to vast legal uncertainty causing caution within the open-source community – especially considering the strictness of the EU product liability standard.

4.2 The New European Product Liability Directive (2024)

The EU lawmaker saw this problem and adopted the PLD New in 2024, aimed at bringing EU product liability law into the digital age (European Commission, Proposal, 2022; Ringe/Kuhmann, 2025, p. 229).

Just like the PLD Old, the PLD New provides a strict liability framework for damages caused by defective products that Member States must implement and can, in principle, not deviate from (for an exception see, e.g., Art. 18 PLD New). Simultaneously, it introduces many changes that could drastically alter the product liability landscape for OSS and OSH stakeholders.

5 Liability under the New European Product Liability Directive

If the PLD New is applicable (5.1), a natural person can bring a claim if they prove that they suffered damage (5.2) caused by a defective product (5.3). The claim can be brought against the manufacturer of the product or the defective component and – in some cases – against the importer, authorized representative or fulfilment provider. If the claimant can't identify these entities, they can even bring their claim against any distributor of the product (5.4). If the defendant cannot prove that one of the narrow exemptions set out in the PLD New applies, they must compensate the injured (5.5), even if there was no fault or negligence on their part.

5.1 Scope

According to Art. 2(1) PLD New, the directive applies to all products placed on the market or put into service after 9 December 2026.

5.1.1 *Classifying OSS and OSH as “Products”*

The new product definition in Art. 4(1) PLD New now explicitly addresses digital manufacturing files and software as products.

5.1.1.1 *Resolving the Software and CAD File Debate*

Therefore, all types of OSS are now classified as products no matter “whether standalone or embedded, and regardless of how [...] delivered or accessed” (Colonna, 2024, p. 10; see also: Piovano/Hess, 2024, p. 207; Wagner, et al., 2023, p. 109; Recital 13 PLD New; Hess, 2025, mn. 8; Wagner, 2024; Ringe/Kuhmann, 2025, p. 232; Thöne 2025, p. 409). The extension towards digital manufacturing files further brings an end to the debate whether EU product liability law not only applies towards physical OSH, but also the underlying design file used to create 3D-printed goods (Piovano/Hess, 2024, p. 208; Kuschel/Haller, 2024, p. 159). Such OSH design files are now covered when they contain “the functional information necessary

to produce a tangible item by enabling the automated control of machinery or tools” (Art. 4(2) PLD New; Recital 16 PLD New).

5.1.1.2 *The Information Exception*

However, pure “information”, like “the mere source code of software” or “the content of digital files, such as media files”, is not considered a product according to Recital 13 Sentence 4 PLD New. This has far-reaching consequences for the open-source community.

Both, OSS and OSH design files, are not immediately developed as computer executable programs or files containing functional information that enable the automated control of, e.g., a 3D-printer.

When a programmer develops software, they usually start by writing a human-readable text in a programming language, such as C or C++. Simplified, this so-called source code is nothing more than a document describing the program so precisely and completely that it can be automatically translated into a machine-readable code (Schmidt, 2019, mn. 148, 151). The source code is then provided to a language translator that converts it into a machine-understandable code, named object or machine code (Schmidt, 2019, mn. 150, 162). This process is called “compiling” (see: Labesius, 2009, p. 1000, fn. 71; Ernst, 2024, mn. 11). Only this compiled code can be understood and executed by a computer and thus provide any functionality on its own (see: Ernst, 2024, mn. 11).

Similarly, OSH designs are normally created as mere 3D models. In a separate step, the completed 3D model is then converted into a set of instructions for the 3D printer, so-called slicing (see: Gerstein/Zentek, 2022, mn. 32). This involves “slicing” the model into thin layers to determine how each layer should be printed, including tool path and layer strength. Only this converted code (often G-Code) can command specific movements of, e.g., the 3D printer that prints the physical OSH product (see: Gerstein/Zentek, 2022, mn. 32). Just like source code, 3D models themselves do not provide any functionality as they do not contain the functional information necessary to produce a tangible item or enable an automated control of hardware. Therefore, they do not count as digital manufacturing files but constitute mere media files. Consequently, source code and 3D models – prior to their translation into G-Code – constitute pure information and are not classified as products under the PLD New.

The consequences are tremendous: First, a programmer contributing only to source code or the 3D model would be exempt from liability under the PLD New, unless they were also involved in placing the compiled object code, the G-Code of the OSH design or the physical OSH on the market or putting it into service. Secondly, OSS stakeholders could circumvent liability under the PLD New in general by no longer providing OSS as executable software or G-Code. Instead, they could merely release the non-compiled source code or 3D models that users must compile or slice themselves (left open regarding the similar debate under the Cyber Resilience Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 - in the following: “CRA”): Poncza, et al., 2023, p. 121).

The distinction between products as functional material or immaterial objects and pure information is rather logical: Information, by itself, does not pose a risk of material harm. It remains a non-functional piece of text or data. The potential for harm only exists where a person trusts in the correctness of this information and transforms it into executable object code (in the case of OSS) or into G-Code (in the case of OSH designs). Only then, the code provides the functionality to initiate processes on a computer or control physical machines potentially causing harm to individuals, property, or data. Therefore, the risk does not directly follow from the source code programmer or 3D model designer, but from the person using their output to create functional objects. Consequently, only these functional objects are relevant under product liability. This understanding aligns with established CJEU case law under the PLD Old, which held that damage resulting solely from a person’s reliance on the accuracy of information does not constitute grounds for product liability (CJEU, C-65/20 – KRONE; Wendehorst, 2024, p. 879).

Yet, some scholars reject this distinction under the PLD New, because it is not stated in the binding text of the PLD New but only in its recitals (see regarding source code: Wagner, 2023, mn. 19). While it is true that recitals are not legally binding and cannot constitute a legal rule on their own (see: Kuschel, 2025, p. 178), they can still cast light on the interpretation of a given legal rule (see: CJEU, C-215/88 – Casa

Fleischhandel, mn. 31). Consequently, the EU lawmaker's explicit intention to exclude source code and other pure information must be considered when interpreting the product definition in Art. 4(1) PLD New. Accordingly, the software term as part of the product definition in Art. 4(1) PLD New must be interpreted as only including the executable program and not the underlying source code (see, for example: Thöne, 2025, p. 409). Correspondingly, the term "digital manufacturing file" (Art. 4(2) PLD New) does not cover OSH designs that are not yet converted into functional G-Code. Note that in exceptional cases no compiling or slicing step is needed, i.e. where the code written by humans or the mere model itself is directly executable by a computer or machine, this code or model is regarded a product.

This view is also supported by a normative consideration. After all, the incentives to participate in open-source projects should not be burdened by strict liability standards (see: Wagner, 2023, mn. 19) – particularly given the EU lawmaker's intention to limit product liability risks regarding open-source software to "not hamper innovation or research" (Recital 14 Sentence 2 PLD New).

5.1.1.3 Conclusion

To summarize, all OSS and OSH constitute products under the PLD New. Yet, mere source code or 3D models are not subject to the PLD New.

5.1.2 Placing on the Market or Putting into Service

Additionally, products only fall within the scope of the PLD New if they have been placed on the market or put into service after 9 December 2026 (Art. 2(1) PLD New).

5.1.2.1 General Overview

"Placing on the market" means the first making available of a product in the Union market, Art. 4(8) PLD New. "Making available" means any supply of a product for distribution, consumption or use on the Union market in the course of a commercial activity (Art. 4(7) PLD New). Therefore, OSS and OSH design files are usually placed on the market as soon as they are provided on open repositories or when a manufacturer or importer makes them available to a distributor or end user for the first time. The latter also applies to physical OSH. This is on condition that it is happening in the course of a commercial activity.

"Putting into service" means the first use of a product in the Union in the course of a commercial activity [...] in circumstances in which that product has not been placed on the market prior to its first use (Art. 4(9) PLD New). This is relevant for products that were not placed on the Union market before they were used in the Union for the first time (Piovano/Hess, 2024, § 3, mn. 41), for instance, a Fab Lab that develops its own OSH laser cutter enabling its use in the Fab Lab for a set price (see in general: Piovano/Hess, 2024, § 3 mn. 41).

As "making available" and "using" depict very broad requirements and are thus easily fulfilled, the decisive factor for triggering strict product liability under the PLD New will often be whether the distribution or use of OSS or OSH takes place "in the course of a commercial activity".

5.1.2.2 The Commercial Activity Requirement

The PLD New only provides rudimentary guidance. Art 4(7) and (9) PLD New merely highlight that a commercial activity cannot simply be ruled out when OSS or OSH is offered for free. The recitals of the PLD New give only minor insights into what constitutes a commercial activity:

- **Sponsoring campaigns and public funded services:** At least Recital 26 Sentence 1 PLD New shows that a commercial activity takes place when products are "supplied in the context of a sponsoring campaign or products manufactured for the provision of a service financed by public funds, since that mode of supply nonetheless has an economic or business character." Insofar, the PLD New falls in line with the view adopted under the PLD Old's non-commercial defense (see 4.1).
- **Paying with personal data:** Secondly, Recital 14 PLD New specifies that OSS is supplied in the course of a commercial activity if it is supplied "in exchange for a price, or for personal data used other than exclusively for improving the security, compatibility or interoperability of the

software”. Insofar, the PLD New consequently follows the idea set out in the Digital Content Directive (Directive (EU) 2019/770) that “paying” with personal data can be a commercial consideration for the provision of OSS (Lejeune, 2024, p. 104).

- **Products distributed by commercial companies:** Following the clarification in Art. 4(7) and (9) and Recitals 14 and 26 PLD New that a commercial activity is not simply ruled out because a product is offered for free, some scholars argue that the distribution of (open-source) products by commercial companies is always rendered commercial. Following this view, only NPOs, private individuals, and research institutions could fall out of the commercial activity requirement. Yet, the PLD New contains no indication of such a differentiation based solely on the nature of the product providing legal entity (Wenglorz, 2025, p. 219). Such an understanding would also run counter to the EU legislator's aim of promoting open-source products provided free of charge (Borges, 2025, p. 5).

While Recitals 26 and 14 PLD New give OSS and OSH stakeholders at least some idea on when they fall in or out of the commercial activity requirement, many key constellations remain unclear. For instance, the PLD New does not stipulate whether financial support during OSS or OSH development, offering additional technical support services (Brenner, 2024, p. 347), or accepting donations (Colonna, 2024, p. 11) is sufficient to trigger product liability for OSS or OSH that is otherwise offered for free.

However, a possible answer to these questions might be derived from the CRA. Just like the PLD New, the scope of the CRA excludes products that are not supplied “in the course of a commercial activity” (see Art. 2(1) in conjunction with Art. 3(21) and (22) and Recital 15 Sentence 1 CRA). Unlike the PLD New, the CRA’s recitals provide comprehensive guidance for several relevant scenarios:

- **Support Services:** According to Recital 15 Sentence 2 CRA, charging a price for technical support services suffices for a commercial activity “where this does not serve only the recuperation of actual costs”.
- **OSS monetization platforms:** The same applies to OSS intended as a software platform “through which the manufacturer monetises other services” (Recital 15 Sentence 2 CRA).
- **Donation-funded OSS and OSH projects:** Additionally, the acceptance of donations exceeding the costs associated with the design, development, and provision of a product also leads to it being supplied or used in the course of a commercial activity (Recital 15 Sentence 2 CRA). Conversely, “accepting donations without the intention of making a profit should not be considered to be a commercial activity” (Recital 15 Sentence 2 CRA).
- **Irrelevance of the development circumstances:** Recital 18 CRA further states that the “circumstances under which the product [...] has been developed, or how the development has been financed, should [...] not be taken into account [...]”. A third-party funded development of OSS or OSH is therefore irrelevant for assessing whether its later supply or use is considered a commercial activity.
- **Integration into subsequent products:** Following Recital 18 CRA, supplying products “intended for integration by other manufacturers into their own products” should only be considered a commercial activity “if the component is monetised by its original manufacturer.”
- **Irrelevance of regular releases:** Moreover, Recital 18 CRA states that “the mere presence of regular releases should not in itself lead to the conclusion that a product [...] is supplied in the course of a commercial activity.”
- **Nonprofit organizations:** Finally, Recital 18 CRA highlights that “the development of products [...] qualifying as free and open-source software by not-for-profit organisations should not be considered to be a commercial activity provided that the organisation is set up in such a way that ensures that all earnings after costs are used to achieve not-for-profit objectives.” This gives NPOs a certain degree of leeway, even though it does not fully exempt them from product liability in every case.

Though neither the CRA nor the PLD New expressly state that the term “in the course of a commercial activity” must be interpreted uniformly in both legislative acts, there is no apparent reason why regulatory responsibility under the CRA and liability responsibility under the PLD New should be treated differently (Brenner, 2024, p. 348). Especially considering that the PLD New aims at creating coherence and consistency within the product safety legislation to maximize legal certainty, it should be assumed that the considerations set out in the CRA’s recitals can be transferred to the PLD New (Thöne, 2025, p. 409; Brenner, 2024, p. 348; Wenglorz, 2025, pp. 220-221 also at least partially transfers the legal considerations set out in the CRA’s recitals to the PLD New; the question is left open by: Schöttle, 2023, p. 219).

Although many cases can now be classified more clearly, some constellations are not addressed by the PLD New or CRA, such as dual licensing. Insofar, one can only rely upon the EU Blue Guide, the EU Commission’s non-binding guidance for interpreting EU product rules. It defines commercial activity “as providing goods in a business related context. This can only be appreciated on a case-by-case basis taking into account the regularity of the supplies, the characteristics of the product, the intentions of the supplier, etc.” (see: European Commission, 2022, Blue Guide, 2.1). Note that regularity of supplies is only a weak indicator following Recital 18 CRA. Under this case-by-case analysis, the supply of a product is already considered commercial, if only parts of the copies are sold commercially. This renders dual licensing where parts of the copies are distributed under a paid proprietary license commercial (Lejeune, 2024, p. 104 reaches the same conclusion without referring to the Blue Guide). To that extend, the PLD New falls short of fully eliminating legal uncertainties in the open-source community. Additionally, the CJEU still holds the exclusive competence to interpret the PLD New and could, theoretically, deviate from the recitals of both PLD New and CRA as well as the Blue Guide.

Nonetheless, the recourse on established definitions in EU law increases legal clarity concerning the applicability of product liability standards to OSS and OSH compared to the complex casuistic under the PLD Old. In this respect, the PLD New may mitigate “chilling effects” arising from uncertainty about product liability within the open-source community. This, in turn, would enable the open-source community to better realize its innovative potential for both market and research purposes – a goal explicitly set out by the EU legislator in Recital 14 of the PLD New.

5.1.2.3 *The OSS Exemption*

Nonetheless, eliminating existing legal uncertainties regarding the applicability of EU product liability law to open-source products is not the only means by which the EU legislator seeks to achieve this objective. In fact, the legislator introduced an explicit exemption for free and open-source software that is *developed* (Variant 1) or *supplied* (Variant 2) outside the course of a commercial activity (Art. 2(2) PLD New) aiming to “not hamper innovation or research” (Recital 14 Sentence 2 PLD New). OSS developed or supplied in this manner is “by definition not placed on the market” (Recital 14 Sentence 2 PLD New).

Albeit it remains questionable whether this exemption from strict product liability offers any practical advantage as the PLD New already exempts products from its scope that are not supplied or used in the EU in the course of a commercial activity (see: 5.1.2.2). This raises the question whether the OSS exemption is anything more than a mere clarification and, if so, whether it can be extended towards OSH.

5.1.2.3.1 *Is it a Declaratory Statement or Substantial Clause?*

An extensive interpretation of Art. 2(2) PLD New could significantly limit liability. If OSS was categorically exempt from product liability under the PLD New solely because it was supplied outside a commercial activity (Variant 2), it could imply that even its subsequent use within a commercial activity could not trigger product liability. And more importantly: if an OSS was developed non-commercially this would mean that its later (commercial) supply and use could never trigger product liability (Variant 1). This would effectively exempt a significant part of the OSS sector from product liability. For instance, if an NPO was to develop OSS outside of a commercial activity, other entities could later distribute it for profit without being subject to strict product liability.

A historical argument in favour of such a broad liability exemption constitutes the original proposal of the PLD New which did not include an OSS exemption. Instead, the non-binding recitals merely stated that “free and open-source software developed or supplied outside the course of a commercial activity” (Recital 13 PLD New Proposal) should not fall under the proposed directive. The fact that this statement has now been incorporated as a distinct exemption, rather than a non-binding recital, suggests that the EU legislator intended to establish a substantive exemption rather than a declaratory clarification of the scope of Art. 2(1) PLD New.

Against this interpretation stands Recital 14 Sentence 3 PLD New, which emphasizes that OSS falling under Art. 2(2) PLD New is “by definition not placed on the market”. The reference to the “normal” scope of the PLD New suggests that the EU legislator only sought to explicitly clarify, in a prominent location, that product liability does not apply to defective OSS whose distribution and use occurs outside a commercial activity.

This interpretation is further supported by the fact that the consequences of a broad interpretation of the OSS exemption evidently do not align with the EU legislator’s objectives. While the legislator seeks to promote OSS (Recital 14 Sentence 2 PLD New), liability privileges should cease to apply where stakeholders place OSS on the market or use it within a commercial activity. Recital 15 PLD New states that a manufacturer integrating OSS originally supplied outside a commercial activity into a commercial product should be liable for damages caused by that product, including the incorporated OSS. An interpretation of the OSS exemption that also exempts such commercial reutilizations of OSS from the PLD New would thus contradict the EU legislator’s intent.

Ultimately, the CJEU has the exclusive competence to provide a definitive answer to this question. According to the authors, the better arguments speak for a purely declaratory character of the OSS exemption (this view is shared by: Thöne, 2025, p. 409; Brenner, 2024, p. 346).

5.1.2.3.2 Can the Exemption be Applied to OSH?

If, however, a different view was to prevail due to the broad wording of Art. 2(2) PLD New, another issue would arise: Does the OSS exemption also apply towards OSH?

On the one hand, the OSS and OSH movements rest on comparable objectives as both are applied in the open-source field with the only difference being that OSH includes tangible items, i.e. physical products. The rationale laid out in Recital 14 PLD New also applies to OSH designs as they are similarly openly shared, freely accessible, usable, modifiable, and redistributable while also offering significant potential for innovation (see: Kuschel/Haller, 2024, p. 159; see also: Haller, 2024, p. 10). Therefore, the privilege of software over hardware, when both are open-source, appears to follow no clear casuistic.

On the other hand, the exception specifically mentions “software”, albeit the European legislator must have been aware of the now established and recognized Open-Source Hardware movement. If they wanted to include OSH, they could have simply written “open-source products” or added “Open-Source Hardware”. The fact that they did not may indicate that there is no unintended regulatory gap, but rather a conscious decision against an exception in favour of OSH (see for a similar argument: Kuschel/Haller, 2024, p. 159).

Note that this question is of no practical significance if one follows the author’s view that the OSS exemption is purely declaratory.

5.1.3 Conclusion

The authors therefore suggest that the scope of the PLD New encompasses all OSH and OSS products, unless they are only distributed and used outside the course of a commercial activity. The latter especially applies towards freely distributed hobby or other non-profit projects (see: European Commission, 2022, Blue Guide, 2.1). For a rough assessment, stakeholders could rely on a two-step test (cf. Figure 1):

Figure 1: Two-step test (figure created by the authors)

Step 1: Is it a product?

Product (+)	Product (-)
physical objects/OSH	source code
digital manufacturing files, e.g. OSH designs translated into G-code	OSH design files without being translated into G-code
OSS (object code/executable software)	

Step 2: If it is a product – Has it been placed on the market or put into service which requires a commercial activity?

5.2 Damage

If an OSS or OSH falls under the PLD New, the claimant must prove that they have suffered damage (Art. 6 in conjunction with Art. 10(1) PLD New). The PLD New expands the types of damage for which the claimant is entitled to compensation (Colonna, 2024). Besides personal injury and damage to private property, it now includes psychological harm (Art. 6(1)(a) PLD New) and destruction or corruption of non-professionally used data (Art. 6(1)(c) PLD New).

5.3 Defective Product

The claimant must then prove that this damage resulted from a product defect (Art. 7 in conjunction with Art. 10(1) PLD New). A product is defective when “it does not provide the safety that a person is entitled to expect or that is required under Union or national law” (Art. 7(1) PLD New).

5.3.1 The General Defectiveness Test

Courts must conduct an objective analysis based on the safety standard the general public can expect from the product (see Recital 30 Sentence 2 PLD New; Colonna, 2024, p. 10; Höll, 2025, p. 14; Piovano/Hess, 2024, § 5 mn. 6; Lejeune, 2024, pp. 102, 105; Handorn, 2023, p. 21; Wagner, 2023, mn. 24). For this assessment, Art. 7(2) and Recitals 30–33 PLD New provide a non-exhaustive list of criteria clarifying and expanding those used under the PLD Old (see: Höll, 2025, p. 14; Brenner, 2024, p. 349; Piovano/Hess, 2024, § 5 mn. 10; Reusch, 2023, pp. 152, 157). In the context of OSS and OSH, the decisive factors are the presentation and the characteristics of the product, the reasonably foreseeable use, software updates and learning capabilities, foreseeable interactions with other products, as well as relevant product safety requirements, including cybersecurity, and the specific needs of the user group for which the product is

intended (see for a comprehensive overview: Piovano/Hess, 2024, § 5 mn. 10; Lejeune, 2024, pp. 105–106; Borges, 2025).

The strictness of the safety standard for a specific OSS or OSH will largely depend on the likelihood and severity of the harm it may cause (see regarding the PLD Old for OSH: Haller, 2024, p. 5; and for software: Spindler, 2024, mn. 73, 74). Products that pose a particularly high risk of causing harm to individuals, such as OSH laser cutters or OSS for life-sustaining medical devices, will be subject to higher safety expectations (Recital 30 Sentence 4 PLD New).

As the PLD New allows for the consideration of specific needs of the user group for which the product is intended, a key question is to what extent the particularities of the OSS and OSH community might influence the applicable safety standard (see: Kuschel/Haller, 2024, p. 151; Haller et al. 2025, p. 83). A core aspect of OSS and OSH is that ordinary citizens without professional knowledge can now become manufacturers (Kuschel/Haller, 2024, p. 151; Haller et al. 2025, p. 83). Therefore, users of OSS and OSH might not expect them to adhere to the same safety standards compared to products from large corporations. Yet, one could also argue the opposite as the OSS and OSH development process leverages the collective intelligence of a multitude of stakeholders aiming to create better products.

Moreover, it is unclear whether the innovative potential and the altruistic purpose of the open-source movement, creating value for society and promoting more sustainable value creation, can be considered when deciding upon the applicable safety expectations (Kuschel/Haller, 2024, p. 160). At least Haller et al. suggest that the altruistic nature of the open-source movement could be taken into account to reduce liability for open-source products (Haller et al. 2025, p. 83).

It will be the task of the courts to find a definitive answer to these questions. As the relevant criteria are very broad, courts in different EU Member States will likely come to different conclusions (see: Borges, 2025), until the matters are finally resolved by the CJEU. Liability addressees will not be able to circumvent the liability risks stemming from this uncertainty by providing information about potential safety issues. In the end, a defective product is not automatically rendered safe, just because users were warned about its lack of safety (see Recital 31 Sentence 1 PLD New).

5.3.2 Dynamization of the Defectiveness Assessment

Additionally, the PLD New now explicitly extends manufacturer's responsibility beyond market release and encompasses subsequent updates, upgrades and modifications (see: Art. 7(2)(e) PLD New; Colonna, 2024, p. 10). Basically, manufacturers are now liable as long as the defect occurs at a time during which the product is under their control – for instance, because they are able to provide software updates or upgrades (see Recital 19 PLD New; Brenner, 2024, p. 351; Spindler, 2024, mn. 76a; Wagner, et al., 2023, p. 109; for a more detailed explanation see: Wagner, 2023, NJW, pp. 1313, 1318). This significantly increases liability risks for open-source stakeholders, specifically regarding OSS. OSS and OSH manufacturers must thus provide necessary software updates and upgrades to limit product liability risks as long as the product is under their control (see Brenner, 2024, 351). The liability risks stemming from these heightened safety requirements are further increased as Art. 9 PLD New eases the burden of proof for a claimant regarding the product defect and its causality for the damage (Colonna, 2024, p. 10).

5.4 Liability Subject and Liability Exemptions

If a defect is present, the subsequent step is to determine who is liable for the resulting damage according to Art. 8 PLD New.

Just as PLD Old ruled, the main liability addressee is the manufacturer of the defective product (Art. 8(1)(a) PLD New; see Ringe/Kuhmann, 2025, p. 233). However, Art. 4(10) PLD New extends the manufacturer definition (Colonna, 2024, p. 11). As before, the entity who produces the physical OSH remains the traditional product manufacturer. In addition, the definition now includes the developer of OSS and OSH designs. This leads to the following liability distribution:

- **OSH Designer:** The OSH designer is liable as manufacturer for damages caused by defects in the design file (see for product components in general: Piovano/Hess, 2024, § 3 mn. 3, 6). Conversely,

the OSH designer is not liable for damages resulting from construction errors on part of the manufacturer of the physical OSH (see for product components in general: Piovano/Hess, 2024, § 4 mn. 3, 6).

- **Manufacturer of physical OSH:** The manufacturer of physical OSH is liable for all damages caused by the final product he placed on the market or put into service (Piovano/Hess, 2024, § 4 mn. 7). Insofar as the damage is resulting from a defective OSH design file, they are liable next to the OSH designer (see for a similar view regarding the PLD Old: Wagner, MÜKoBGB, 2024, ProdHaftG § 4 mn. 16).
- **OSS Developer:** The OSS developer is liable for all damage caused by the defectiveness of the OSS. Due to the dynamization of the defectiveness assessment, the liability also spans defective updates, upgrades, or machine learning algorithms (see: Colonna, 2024). Note that this only applies to the developer of the executable (i.e. compiled) OSS and not to mere source code contributions.
- **Developers of 3D models and source code:** Those who only contributed to or distributed source code or 3D models are not subject to product liability as these contributions lack product quality (see 5.1.1.2).
- **Integrated products:** If another manufacturer subsequently integrates third-party OSS or OSH into their products, they become liable for all defects of the final product (Art. 8(1)(a) and Sentence 2 PLD New). Additionally, the original OSS or OSH manufacturer is liable as component manufacturer (Art. 8(1)(b) PLD New) for defects in the original OSS or OSH. The same applies to the OSH designer regarding defects originating from that design. However, if the original OSS or OSH (design file) was supplied outside the course of a commercial activity, only the manufacturer of the final product is liable under the PLD New (see Recital 15 PLD New in conjunction with Art. 11(a) PLD New; see also: Colonna, 2024, p. 11).
- **Substantial modifications:** Moreover, if a person substantially modifies an OSS or OSH outside the original manufacturer's control and thereafter makes it available on the market or puts it into service, this person will take over the role as manufacturer and thus will be liable for defects of the modified product (see Art. 8(2) PLD New; for a definition of substantial modifications see Art. 4(18) PLD New).
- **Additional liability subjects:** Furthermore, when the product or component manufacturer is established outside the EU, the importer, an authorized representative, or subsequently the fulfilment service provider are liable next to that manufacturer (Art. 8(1)(c) PLD New). Even online platforms, including open repositories, can be held liable when those economic operators cannot be identified (Colonna, 2024, p. 10).

Just like under the PLD Old, liability addressees cannot contractually limit or exclude their liability under the PLD New (Art. 13(1) PLD New). Therefore, traditionally used contractual exemptions in open-source licenses might lose their legal admissibility increasing risks and uncertainty in the open-source community (Colonna, 2024, p. 11). Simultaneously, Art. 11 PLD New now contains less liability exemptions than the PLD Old (Brenner, 2024, 351).

5.5 Legal Consequence

If an economic operator is liable according to the aforementioned standard, they must compensate the claimant for all material and immaterial loss resulting from the damage caused by the defective product (Art. 5 PLD New).

6 Critical Evaluation and Outlook

After examining the new liability landscape under the PLD New it is time to return to the initial question: Is the PLD New truly a turning point for the product liability landscape protecting consumers while also enabling the open-source movement to fully realize its transformative and innovative potential? Or did it introduce rules so strict, that they practically mean the end of open source?

The answer is: both – though only to a certain extent. For individual contributors who provide source code or 3D models as part of an open-source project, the PLD New represents a meaningful improvement. These contributors now benefit from greater legal certainty since such contributions will not trigger strict product liability. However, the situation is markedly different for manufacturers of executable OSS, OSH designs in G-code, and physical OSH. Under the PLD New, they now face significantly reduced opportunities to avoid strict liability. Given that the revised directive introduces numerous changes that shift the liability landscape in favour of injured parties, product liability considerations will become even more central when deciding whether and how to publish open-source projects. This is particularly relevant because open repositories may now be held liable as distributors for products made available on their platforms. As a result, many open-source hosting platforms may need to reconsider whether to continue offering their services in the same way.

A huge problem for all stakeholders is that many liability frameworks under national law will remain applicable next to the PLD New. Especially the German and Austrian fault-based manufacturer's liability (Produzentenhaftung) in § 823(1) German Civil Code or § 1295(1) Austrian Civil Code will likely still apply (Wendehorst, 2024, KI-VO, mn. 77). As they neither include a non-commercial exemption nor exclude source code or 3D models from their scope, they could significantly limit the practical effects of the privileges for OSS and OSH laid out in this article (see: Wagner, 2025, pp. 129, 134).

Moreover, legislative changes surrounding product liability are not the only new legislation affecting the open-source environment. Especially the AI Act and the CRA will evoke more regulatory responsibility and additional liability for certain open-source products (Colonna, 2024, p. 15). This will present challenges for the open-source community, including greater administrative burdens, legal complexities, and potential obstacles to collaboration and innovation (Colonna, 2024, p. 15). Notably this will pose a considerable disadvantage for smaller, community-led initiatives which make up the very heart of many open-source projects (Colonna, 2024, p. 18). In the end, the new regulatory framework might reduce creativity and innovation more than enabling it.

7 Conclusion

Albeit the PLD New does not fully provide the liability exemptions that the open-source movement hoped for, it leads to more legal clarity enabling stakeholders to adapt a constructive and informed approach towards product liability issues. Especially in jurisdictions where the national law does not provide a liability framework like the German or Austrian manufacturer's liability, the PLD New will greatly improve the situation for non-commercial open-source projects and individual contributors thereto.

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AI has only been used for language correction. No AI has been used in the production of the scientific content of this paper.

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